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Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries

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Report: DHNB 2023

7th Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries Conference (8–10 March 2023)

Victoria G. D. Landau MA

“How do DH projects and practices depend on unsustainable systems and mindsets?
How do the unequal consequences of environmental challenge influence
what research gets done in DH, and who can contribute?
How can the field contribute to a more sustainable world?”
—Organizers, DHNB 2023¹

The seventh iteration of the annual conference of EADH/ADHO member association «Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries» (DHNB) took place online, spanning three days of conference contributions (08.–10.03.2023), and two days of pre-conference events (06.–07.03.2023). Under the umbrella topic of *Sustainability: Environment – Community – Data*, the featured papers addressed various dimensions of *sustaining* data, projects and concepts and including *sustainable* approaches in scholarship. Longevity, perpetuity and consistency are staple concerns for research generated in and utilizing Digital Humanities, and they are broadly addressed in different ways by different scholars and initiatives, as illustrated by the 44 Long Papers, 20 Show-and-Tell Presentations, and 6 Workshops accepted from scholars from 19 countries: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Denmark, Great Britain, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Israel, Japan, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland and USA. All submissions were asked to be in English, and while Long Papers reported on completed, original and unpublished results, Show-and-Tell Presentations offered brief overviews over ongoing research and initiatives.

With a unique, clear three-city organization (the Norwegian cities of Oslo, Bergen and Stavanger being equal host locations for the conference), the organizers made excellent use of the online format in combination with local in-person Workshops and Keynotes at all three sites. Following the conference subtitle «Environment – Community – Data», contributions were assigned to three «tracks», an Environment (ET), a Community (CT) and a Data Track (DT), as well as an Open Track (OT). Show-and-Tell Presentations (ST) had their own track, playing the pre-recorded videos on a loop during designated time slots, while speakers were available for questions. For a summary of the conference structure and content, this report will highlight a selection of talks as examples for issues discussed and included in each track.

¹ Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries, 2023, «Sustainability: Environment – Community – Data» [<https://dhnbc.eu/conferences/dhnbc2023/>].

Environment Track

Seeing its dimensions as too impactful for the Digital Humanities to ignore, contributions in this track presented the Environment as both playing field and research subject. *Nature and Culture in the Age of Environmental Crisis: Digital Analysis of a Global Debate in The UNESCO Courier, 1948–2011* by Benjamin G. Martin & Fredrik Norén (Uppsala/Umeå) traced the discussion of the theme of «Nature» in the UNESCO *Courier* since its inception in 1948. The magazine has been digitized, offering a valuable dataset for research based on topic modelling, analyzing statistically generated themes across the content of the entire magazine run. Results reveal not only a lack of treatment of the topics related to «Nature» in the «culture-focused» *Courier* apart from human-nature interaction, but a geographically limited global understanding and focus on the Northern Hemisphere, with European authors up until D. Chakrabarty generally not showing a «world-wide, international» view on the issue. Contrary to the assumption that this perspective may have changed when post-colonial member countries joined UNESCO post-1960s, there is no measurable shift indicated in the results. A stated limitation of the dataset is the fact that the UNESCO *Courier* is a special issue magazine, with a topic focus per issue, directly affecting how often themes of «Nature» might occur across issues. In a planned project, the speakers next intend to analyze the written minutes of UNESCO meetings on the same themes.

Community Track

Community in research and research within communities were both facets covered within this track. *The Digital Lab as an Arena for Teaching and Outreach Activities Connected to the Special Collections at the University of Bergen Library* by Emma Josefin Ölander Aadland (Bergen) presented the University Library at Bergen's «Digital Lab» (D-Lab) as an interdisciplinary hub, established in 2020 and offering a wide variety of events and services to its research community. This includes breakfast seminars related to exhibitions at the library, connected to the library's special collections, as well as trainings and support. While Bergen does not currently offer a study program in DH, many projects at the University engage with DH methods, and a general interest in including digital approaches in teaching and research has heightened demand. On the other hand, *Understanding Without Knowing: Livonian Intangible Cultural Heritage* by Valts Ernštreits (Riga) introduced the Livonian language indigenous to Northern Latvia, which has been kept alive by a small number of speakers and scholars. Considering what it means for digital tools to be used in linguistic research with an endangered language, Ernštreits contrasted preservation efforts for a limited language (due to it being ancient and/or critically endangered) with irresponsible use of AI-based, machine translation – machine

«translating» from other languages to Livonian, for example, would gravely pollute the limited data pool, causing immeasurable problems for future accurate language preservation.

Data Track

Perspectives on digital sustainability and accessibility, including in code, software and infrastructures, were found in this track. *(R)Unicode: Encoding and Sustainability Issues in Runology* by Elisabeth Maria Magin & Marcus Smith (Oslo/Stockholm) pointed out the difficulty of digitally working with «uncommon» writing systems, such as those utilizing runes, when unicode and fonts do not meet the demands of research. Being at present unable to handle varieties in signs (both historically, spanning the 3rd–19th c., and geographically, spanning an area from modern-day Ukraine to Greenland), and in the worst-case forced to relegate to mere transcription instead of transliteration, possible solutions for the problem were outlined, as well as plans to approach unicode regulators with concrete improvements. The speakers further importantly stated the issue of «small subjects», and the difficulties scholars in these fields face when attempting large-scale changes according to the needs of a small community.

Open Track

Contributions on digital methods and topics reaching across tracks, such as political discourse, current events, computer vision and machine reading, were assigned to the Open Track.

Workshops

The six selected workshops open to both conference participants and external interested parties included the topics of web accessibility, the [Norwegian Web Archive](#) (site in Norwegian), DH and CH (Cultural Heritage) education and collaboration, the Danish [KUB Datalab](#), sustainability in LAM (Libraries, Archives and Museums), and [digital tools and platforms for history and antiquity research](#). They offered a great platform for exchange, with varying degrees of interactivity for participants; some were structured as panel presentations, others as effectively tutorials for specific implementations. Four of the six workshops were offered online, two on-site in Oslo and Copenhagen respectively.

Presentation to highlight: The third and final evening Keynote of the week, hosted by the Universitetet i Oslo: Malvika Sharan (The Turing Way Project) on *Open Science for Enabling Reproducible, Ethical and Collaborative Research: Insights from the Turing Way* (Slides on [Zenodo](#)).

The Show-and-Tell Contributions are available on the [DHNB YouTube channel](#). The comprehensive 170-page Book of Abstracts has been uploaded open access on [Zenodo](#). The organizers have also provided a curated short literature list on the conference topic on [Zotero](#).